

agr! BRIDGES

**“Building bridges between consumers and producers
by supporting short food supply chains through a
systemic, holistic, multi-actor approach-based Toolbox”**

(Grant Agreement 101000788)

Coordination and Support Action

**“Let’s Build our SFSC”
Event Validation Report
Responsible Partner: Sabri Ülker Foundation**

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N° 101000788.

"Let's Build our SFSC!" Event Validation Report - TURKEY

Issued by: Sabri Ülker Foundation
Issue date: 23/06/2023
Due date: 30/06/2023
Work Package Leader: MTU (Task Leader: Q-PLAN)

Start date of project: 01 January 2021

Duration: 36 months

Document History

Version	Date	Changes
1.0	23/06/2023	Draft version
2.0	23/06/2023	Final version

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

Main authors	
Name	Organisation
Selen Tokcan, Özge Dinç	SUF

Quality reviewers	
Name	Organisation
George Malliopoulos, Eirini Efthymiadou	Q-PLAN

LEGAL NOTICE

The information and views set out in this report are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained therein.

© agroBRIDGES Consortium, 2022 - 2023

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Table of Contents

1.	INTRODUCTION	5
2.	“LET’S BUILD OUR SFSC” EVENT ORGANISATION DETAILS	6
2.1	Event programme / agenda	6
2.2	Personnel involved in the organisation of the event.....	7
2.3	Event material	8
2.4	Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation	9
3.	EVENT IMPLEMENTATION AND OUTCOMES	10
3.1	Event implementation	10
3.2	Event participation.....	12
4.	EVENT VALIDATION	13
4.1.1	<i>Validation of event by participants</i>	13
4.1.2	<i>Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner</i>	14
4.1.3	<i>Limitations and barriers of the organising partner</i>	14

List of figures

Figure 1:	promo material: invitation for mailing to agri-food stakeholders, producers, cooperatives	8
-----------	---	---

List of tables

Table 1:	Event programme	6
Table 2:	Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event.....	7
Table 3:	Event participation.....	12

1. Introduction

The present report summarises the activities of Sabri Ülker Foundation for the organisation and validation of the **“Let’s build our SFSC” event in İstanbul, Turkey organised on May 31th, 2023**. This event is an online brokerage and networking event, to bring stakeholders of the local agri-food sector to present their products, meet others and negotiate partnerships based on the concept of Short Food Supply Chains. The event was organised using the Brella matchmaking platform that was selected as the most appropriate for the needs of the agroBRIDGES consortium, based on market research and negotiations with the sales departments of various candidate providers, in the frame of task 3.4.

The present report outlines all steps taken for the design, planning and implementation of the regional event, as well as the outcomes and evaluation of the event by the participants and the organising agroBRIDGES partner, to produce suggestions for the improvement of the “Let’s build our SFSC!” tool and measure its impact to the agrifood sector at local level. The remainder of the report is structured as follows:

- **Chapter 1** – Introducing the event report
- **Chapter 2** – Describing the concept selection, design, organisation and implementation of the ‘Let’s build our SFSC in Türkiye’ event in İstanbul, Turkey.
- **Chapter 3** – Outlining the validation results for the events by participants and the value found in the “Let’s meet!” guidelines by the organising partners when creating and launching their event.
- **Chapter 4** – Concluding remarks for the event and suggestions for improvement of the “Let’s meet!” tool.

2. “Let’s build our SFSC” event organisation details

2.1 Event programme / agenda

Table 1: Event programme

Title of activity	Topic / Short description	Date & Time (local)	Speakers	Location
Welcome speech	Presentation of local agri-food products	14:00 – 14:10	Local food producers	Central stage
SUF session	Presentation of agroBRIDGES project	14:10 – 14:20	Selen Tokcan, Secretary General of SUF	Central stage
Kerevitaş session	Presentation of local agri-food products	14.20-14.50	Özhan Nuri Özesenli, Kerevitaş - Supply Chain General Manager	Central stage
Closing Remarks – Q&A session	Vote of thanks to the event participants	14:50 – 15:00	Selen Tokcan, Secretary General of SUF	Central stage
Networking/Matchmaking session	One-to-one meetings	15.30-16.30	N/A	Breakout rooms in Brella Platform

2.2 Personnel involved in the organisation of the event

Table 2: Estimated effort and expertise needed for the event

Specialisation	Number of employees	Expected role	In-house / External	Estimated effort (person days)
Social media expert	1	Development of promo material	In-house	2 days
Session moderator	1	Coordination of the online session	In-house	1 days
Project manager	1	Providing participants	In-house	2 days
Communication Director	1	Coordination of social media posts	In-house	1 day
Nutrition Executive	1	Planning the flow, the consent form, registration form and questionnaire form translations to local language, providing participants	In-house	2 days

2.3 Event material

Figure 1: promo material: social media post

Figure 1: promo material: invitation for mailing to agri-food stakeholders, producers, cooperatives

Figure 3: promo material: event programme

2.4 Invitation of attendees and promotional activities implementation

One month before the event, an invitation was sent by e-mail to start the communication activities and to complete the event with the maximum number of participants. Final records were taken by sending a reminder mail 1 week before the event. The heads of 72 women's cooperatives in Turkey were invited by phone call. Event information and registration form were then sent to e-mail/phone numbers. In addition, a whatsapp group was created and a link was sent to 72 women's cooperatives on the day of the event and a reminder message was sent. In addition, an invitation e-mail was sent to the senior managers of institutions that have important activities in the short food supply chain, such as Kerevitaş, Şok Marketler and İste Gelsin (online shopping channel). In addition to this, invitations were sent to 4 farmers, who are among the MAP members, via whatsapp.

3. Event implementation and outcomes

3.1 Event implementation

Contacting 72 different women's cooperatives prior to the event provided a significant participation in the event. Women entrepreneurs took an active role in network negotiations to create a sales channel to sell their products. In addition, Kerevitaş's activities to strengthen the short food supply chain in Türkiye, received great interest from the participants. Producers (especially women entrepreneurs) among the participants had the opportunity to meet with Kerevitaş's General Manager to sell their products, and 4 different women's cooperatives presented their products.

Figure 4: Event picture

Figure 5: Event picture

Figure 6: Brella Platform Home Page

3.2 Event participation

The event was attended by 49 individuals including the SUF team organisers. 25 participants were registered to the Brella platform, while the rest joined using the session link without registering to the platform.

Table 3: Event participation

Audience type	No. of participants
Producers	11
Distributors	4
Cooperative members	30
Consumers	4
Total	49

4. Event Validation

4.1.1 Validation of event by participants

Question	Answers					
Were you familiar with the concept of Short Food Supply Chains before this event?	Yes		No		Not Sure	
Attendee answers	49		0		0	
Did you find this event helpful to meet professionals and businesses you can collaborate with?	Very helpful	Helpful	Neutral	Not very helpful	Not helpful at all	I prefer to not to answer
Attendee answers	41	7	1	0	0	0
Do you think that this event helped you see Short Food Supply Chains as a promising business alternative?	Very useful	Useful	Neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I prefer to not to answer
Attendee answers	26	21	2	0	0	0
Did you find the matching and booking of one-to-one meetings with other people useful to identify and negotiate collaborations?	Very useful	Useful	Neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I prefer to not to answer
Attendee answers	21	27	1	0	0	0

Was the event useful in supporting you to find interesting opportunities to collaborate with other businesses for the development of Short Food Supply Chains?	Very useful	Useful	Neutral	Not very useful	Not useful at all	I prefer to not to answer
Attendee answers	34	15	0	0	0	
Would you like another similar event to be organised in your region? How often?	Monthly or more often	3-4 times a year	Twice a year	Once a year	Never	I prefer to not to answer
Attendee answers	33	14	1	1	0	0

4.1.2 Validation of the “Let’s build our SFSC” event by the organising partner

Question #1: Did you find the event relevant to your local agri-food ecosystem and organization?

Especially the feedback we get from women's cooperatives and farmers is that such activities are almost never held (in Turkey). We hope that these events will become widespread as these events will contribute significantly to the short food supply chain and the local agri-food ecosystem.

Question #2: Would you organise the same event again in your region? If yes, would you make any adjustments? If not, please explain your thinking.

If we were to organize the same event again, we would try to create the opportunity to do it face-to-face. Because, unfortunately, especially cooperatives and farmers are not very good at using the internet and social media. It took a lot of time and effort to explain the Brella platform. There were participants who forgot their microphones on during the event and did not realize that their camera was turned on. For this reason, attention should be paid to the digital literacy of the target group and the event design should be shaped accordingly. If it is done online, a more user-friendly platform can be selected. Another feedback came to the registration forms, since it took time to fill these forms, the participants expected to be able to log in directly to the Brella platform and have network conversations.

4.1.3 Limitations and barriers of the organising partner

The event had to be held on an online platform. However, the participant profile may not be suitable for this, which is a negative factor that reduced the number of participants of the event.